

they do not cause specific symptoms on the aboveground parts of the plant, they can cause severe growth reduction, chlorosis, wilting of plants, and 20-70% yield reduction in infested fields. *M. graminicola*, the rice root-knot nematode, is widely distributed in rainfed upland and lowland ricefields in South and Southeast Asia, especially in light-textured soils. It is considered to be an important pest in rainfed lowland areas in India and northeast Thailand.

S. rostrata, unfortunately, is a very good host for *M. graminicola* when grown in nonflooded soils (see figure and table). Cropping it before rice in nonflooded soils infested by rice root-knot nematodes may increase their number tremendously. This increase in *M. graminicola* may cause increased yield losses, eliminating the benefit expected from cultivating the green manure crop. This is the other side of the coin.

S. rostrata has tremendous potential as a green manure crop. Under rainfed conditions, however, it must be used with caution. It is hazardous to grow *S. rostrata* in rainfed ricefields where *M. graminicola* is present. Leguminous crops resistant to *M. graminicola* should be identified as alternatives to *S. rostrata* in rainfed lowland rice areas infested with the nematode. ■

Environment

Climate change and rice

In March 1994 IRRI convened an international symposium that reviewed the broad issues of global climate and its effect on rice growth and production. The posters displayed at the symposium appear in a slightly modified form in this section. We hope you find these notes to be a valuable source of information.

Methane emission from ricefields

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The increase in atmospheric CH₄ concentration has been recognized during the past decade. The current amount of methane in the atmosphere is 4700 Tg. The total annual global emission of CH₄ is estimated to be 500 Tg, about 70% of which is biogenic in origin. Flooded ricefields are probably one of the largest agricultural sources of atmospheric CH₄.

Flooding a ricefield cuts off the oxygen supplied by the atmosphere to the soil; this results in the fermentation of soil organic matter. CH₄ is a major end product of this process. Flooded ricefields release CH₄ to the atmosphere by diffusion, ebullition, or through the

Regional distribution of harvested rice area (million ha) in major rice growing, less developed countries in 1985. IRRI, 1989.

Region	Irrigated rice	Rainfed rice	Deepwater rice	Upland rice	Total
South Asia	19.2	24.3	8.8	7.9	60.2
East Asia	32.2	1.9		0.7	34.8
Southeast Asia	12.0	12.6	3.6	3.3	31.5
Latin America	2.2	0.4		4.5	7.1
Africa	1.0	1.3	0.2	2.1	4.6
Total	66.6	40.5	12.6	18.5	138.2

Scheme of methane production, oxidation, and emission in a flooded ricefield.

rice plants, which mediate the transport of CH₄ from the reduced soil to the atmosphere (see figure). Much of the CH₄ formed in the anaerobic soil may remain entrapped in the soil and is oxidized to CO₂.

Rice is the only major grain crop that is grown almost exclusively for human food. One hundred forty million ha of rice are harvested annually. In developed countries, ricefields are irrigated because it increases production potential. In less

developed countries, only 50% of the harvested rice area is irrigated but it accounts for more than 70% of yield. Rainfed ricefields, which are prone to droughts and floods, make up 30% of the rice area, and upland rice, 13% (see table). It is estimated that irrigated and rainfed ricefields emit annually up to 100 Tg CH₄. ■